

SU(5) GUT

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Abstract

1 The problem with Grand Unified Theories

Recently, it was pointed out that the predictions of perturbation theory in the Georgi-Glashow $SU(5)$ Grand Unified Theory are probably inconsistent [1].

The construction of a non-abelian charge requires dressing the gauge-dependent elementary fields, forming locally gauge-invariant operators. If the construction of non-abelian charges would be possible, then such construction would be a better alternative to the local gauge-fixing condition (used in perturbation theory), which is globally ill-defined due to the Gribov ambiguity. However, the only known ways of dressing the fields, require the existence of a local gauge-fixing condition which is globally well defined [2]. Thus no such alternative to local gauge-fixing is known and so assuming the existence of a non-abelian charge is speculative, even at weak coupling [3].

The above discussion implies that the global electromagnetic charge is difficult to reproduce in a Grand Unified Theory, while the Standard Model allows to reproduce the electromagnetic charge since there is no Gribov ambiguity in abelian gauge-fixing .

2 Fields

In the following we discuss what are the requirements for the predictions of perturbation theory in the Georgi-Glashow $SU(5)$ Grand Unified Theory to be consistent. These requirements involve a generalization of the notion of asymptotic states in Quantum Field Theory. There is thus a structural difference between the perturbation theory (where asymptotic states are crucial) and the gauge-invariant formulation, as was already noted in reference [1].

The invariant tensors of the $SU(5)$ group are algebraic combinations of the Kronecker delta and the Levi-Cita tensor.

We consider two Higgs fields (Φ, Σ) in an irreducible (fundamental,adjoint) representation of $SU(5)$.

After gauge-fixing, we consider that the vevs of the two Higgs fields are
 $\langle \Phi_j \rangle = \delta_{j5}$, $\langle \Sigma \rangle = \text{diag}(2, 2, 2, -3, -3)$.

In that case, we can form operators whose vacuum expectation values are projections for the different representations of $SU(3)$ and $SU(2)$ or $U(1)_{em}$, following the procedure of reference [4].

So, contracting with the Higgs field Φ will create a trivial representation of $SU(3)$ and $U(1)_Y$.

Applying the projection $P_0 = \Phi\Phi^\dagger$ will create a trivial representation of $U(1)_{em}$ and $SU(3)$.

Applying the projection $P_+ = \frac{2-\Sigma}{5} - P_0$ will create a charged state of $U(1)_{em}$ and trivial representation of $SU(3)$.

Applying the projection $P_3 = \frac{3+\Sigma}{5}$ will create a fundamental representation of $SU(3)$ and trivial representation of $SU(2)$.

Applying the projection $P_2 = 1 - P_3 = \frac{2-\Sigma}{5}$ will create a fundamental representation of $SU(2)$ and trivial representation of $SU(3)$.

Note that $P_+ + P_0 = P_2$.

Then $\text{Re}(P_2 D_\mu P_3)$ and $\text{Im}(P_2 D_\mu P_3)$ account for 12 massive vector bosons. These can be divided into 6 bosons $P_0 D_\mu P_3$, and 6 bosons $P_+ D_\mu P_3$.

Also $(P_3 \Sigma P_3 - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(P_3 \Sigma P_3) 1)$, $(P_2 \Sigma P_2 - \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(P_2 \Sigma P_2) 1)$, $(\frac{2}{3} \text{tr}(P_3 \Sigma P_3) - \frac{3}{2} \text{tr}(P_2 \Sigma P_2))$, account for $8 + 3 + 1 = 12$ Higgs bosons. These 3 bosons $(P_2 \Sigma P_2 - \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(P_2 \Sigma P_2) 1)$ can be divided into 2 bosons $(P_+ \Sigma P_0)$ plus 1 boson $(P_+ \Sigma P_+ - P_0 \Sigma P_0)$.

The 12 Higgs bosons plus the 12 goldstones (present in the massive vector bosons) correspond to the 24 degrees of freedom of Σ .

Then $P_+ D_\mu \Phi$ and $\Phi^\dagger D_\mu \Phi$ account for 3 massive vector bosons (W^+ and W^0).

Also $P_3 \Phi$, $\Phi^\dagger \Phi$ account for $6 + 1 = 7$ Higgs bosons.

The 7 Higgs bosons plus the 3 goldstones (present in the massive vector bosons) correspond to the 10 degrees of freedom of Φ .

The fermions can be easily obtained using the projections P_3 , P_+ and P_0 on the $SU(5)$ fermionic fields. It remains to solve how to obtain local gauge-invariant states of $SU(3) \times U(1)_{em}$.

3 Dressings

Now we need an ‘‘effective’’ $U(1)_{em}$ global charge. We choose a reference point x_0 in space-time (any point is fine) and we define the Wilson lines

$$U_3(x) = \Pi_{x_0}^x P_3(y + dy)(1 + igdy^\mu W_\mu^a(y)t^a)P_3(y)$$

and

$$U_+(x) = \Pi_{x_0}^x P_+(y + dy)(1 + igdy^\mu W_\mu^a(y)t^a)P_+(y)$$

and

$$U_0(x) = \Pi_{x_0}^x P_0(y + dy)(1 + igdy^\mu W_\mu^a(y)t^a)P_0(y)$$

connecting x to x_0 following a straight path. Note that U_3 is effectively the Wilson line for the gluons and U_+ for the photon. After the mean-field approximation, both are special unitary

matrix, i.e. elements of the $SU(3)$ and $U(1)$ groups respectively; while U_0 becomes the identity operator.

We dress every open index of $SU(5)$, i.e. we replace the effective projections P_3, P_+, P_0 by the corresponding Wilson line $P_3(x) \rightarrow U_3(x)$ and $P_+(x) \rightarrow U_+(x)$ and $P_0(x) \rightarrow U_0(x)$. This has the effect of changing the gauge dependence to a single point x_0 . Note that before (i.e. for $SU(5)$) or after (i.e. for $SU(3) \times U_{em}(1)$) the mean-field approximation, different dressings (e.g. Coulomb-like dressing) can be obtained from algebraic combinations of these dressed fields, since we can reconstruct the gauge fields from the Wilson loops [5].

Since the invariant tensors of the $SU(n)$ group are algebraic combinations of the Kronecker delta and the Levi-Civita tensor, then we also need to check that the Levi-Civita tensor of $SU(3)$ can be reproduced from the Levi-Civita tensor of $SU(5)$ (which has 5-indices). Indeed, if we occupy the 3 first indices with quarks and another index with the Higgs vev, it remains one open index corresponding to the P_+ projector and to the abelian gauge field (which is correct, since three right-handed down quarks have two units of hypercharge). Therefore, the Levi-Civita tensor of $SU(3)$ can be reproduced from the Levi-Civita tensor of $SU(5)$.

Without the mean-field approximation we have in fact gauge-covariant asymptotic states, which is a non-trivial generalization of the notion of asymptotic states in Quantum Field Theory (the asymptotic states are usually locally gauge-invariant).

The physical spectrum is determined using 2-point correlation functions. These correlation functions will be gauge-invariant due to the dressing, since there is a contraction of gauge-dependent fields in a single point x_0 . Thus the physical spectrum predicted by the mean-field approximation coincides with the naive perturbation theory.

4 Conclusion

We conclude that gauge-covariant asymptotic states are needed to make perturbation theory work in the $SU(5)$ GUT, and then the fact that the asymptotic states are not locally gauge-invariant (only the correlation functions are gauge-invariant) can not affect the spectrum of the theory. This a non-trivial and untested requirement beyond the Higgs mechanism of the Standard Model.

References

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